

The H2FORM3G project explores hydrogen's effect in the manufacturing of third-generation advanced high-strength steel (AHSS) components for future lightweight vehicle designs.

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Duration:
42 months

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RFCS programme

High-strength steels reduce vehicle weight by 10-20% due to their superior properties, but they are more prone to hydrogen embrittlement, which can cause premature fractures.

The main goal of H2FORM3G is to provide tools that prevent crack generation during automotive components forming.

H2FORM3G will contribute to reduce the number of failed parts, lower material waste by 25%, and enhance vehicle safety.

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Exploring hydrogen effect on the formability of 3rd generation advanced high-strength steels for future vehicle designs

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Preventing the risk of crack generation during the forming of automotive components

The project seeks to generate a comprehensive understanding of the interaction between hydrogen and Q&P steels microstructure during forming to ensure their safe implementation for manufacturing lightweight automotive parts at affordable costs.

H2FORM3G will develop advanced characterisation methodologies, such as the use of synchrotron radiation, and predictive models that will contribute to consolidate the role of steel as a cost-efficient and sustainable lightweight solution for the future mobility.

Understanding Hydrogen Embrittlement

A microscopic scale model based on a crystal plasticity constitutive law coupled to a hydrogen diffusion model will be developed to better understand hydrogen embrittlement mechanisms.

Predicting forming behaviour

A constitutive model to predict forming behaviour of TRIP-assisted 3rd Gen AHSS considering hydrogen influence will be developed.

Preventing failure in manufacturing

A validated failure criterion will be established from finite element simulations of the forming process, ensuring better prediction and prevention of failure during manufacturing.

Reduce cracking risk and delayed fracture

Models validated across different hydrogen concentrations will allow assessing the risk of hydrogen-assisted cracking during manufacturing and delayed fracture risks after forming.

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The new methodologies and models studied in H2FORM3G will accelerate the design of lighter and safer automotive steel components.

Project phases

Interaction of H₂ with steel microstructure

Understanding the correlation between the steel microstructure and the hydrogen charging, as well as the microstructural evolution during plastic deformation.

Formability characterization

Characterizing some of the most critical properties of the studied steels by means of mechanical tests.

Modelling and simulation

Advanced FEM modelling of forming processes including mechanical behaviour and hydrogen diffusion modelling.

Industrial implementation

The industrial implementation of Q&P steels for manufacturing automotive relevant components.